

**MANAGING FUNCTIONAL EDUCATION
AT SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL FOR SUSTAINABLE
NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH EFFECTIVE LEADERSHIP
PRACTICES IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract:

This study therefore investigated ways of managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development through effective leadership practices in Anambra State. Four research questions guided the study. The researcher employed a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 6,230 principals and teachers from all public secondary schools in the six education zones of Anambra State. Nine hundred and eight (908) respondents comprising two hundred and twenty (220) principals and six hundred and eighty-eight (688) teachers selected through the use of simple random sampling techniques constituted the sample size for the study. The instrument for data collection was a - 36 item questionnaire tagged "Managing Functional Secondary Education for Sustainable National Development Questionnaire" (MFSESNDQ). The instrument was duly validated by three experts in the Department of Educational Foundations and Management and all from Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Anambra State. The reliability of the instrument was determined through a pilot-testing that was carried out in selecting a sample of 6 principals and 24 teachers from 6 public secondary schools in Delta State. Thereafter, the scores were measured using Cronbach Alpha method to obtain an internal consistency reliability value of 0.72 and were considered adequate for the study. Findings from the study showed that: the principals' applied little instructional leadership practices, students' personnel practices and teacher collaborative practices for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State. Out of these findings, recommendation were made which include: Anambra State Government in Collaboration with Post-Primary Education Board (PPEB) should mandated to support and strengthen external collaborative practices between principals and the local

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communities as a way of improving managing functional secondary education for sustainable development in Anambra State.

Keywords: functional secondary education, sustainable national development, leadership practices

1. Introduction

Education is a top priority in the national development of any nation because education aids in the acquisition of appropriate skills for development of mental, physical, social abilities and competencies which helps individual to live and contribute to the society. Secondary education is the education received by children after primary and before the tertiary stage. It is also one of the levels of education which an individual must pass through to higher education, prepares the youth for adulthood and the world of work in the society (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). In more specific terms, secondary education according to National Policy on Education 6th Edition gave the broad goals of secondary education to include: prepares graduates of basic education and senior secondary schools for the world of works, wealth creation and entrepreneurship; provide sound education for the higher level; offer diversified curriculum to cater for various interests and differences in talents and dispositions; train manpower in applied sciences and different subject areas; provide entrepreneurial, technical, vocational, agricultural and specific skills for self-reliance; develop and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of worlds' of cultural heritage; foster patriotism, national consciousness and value re-orientation, among others (Federal Republic of Nigeria-FRN, 2013). Achievement of the goals of secondary education can only be realized if good leadership practices are applied and quality teaching and learning are maintained and improved, then education should be functional as well as sustaining national development.

Functional education is that kind of education that produces individuals with demonstrable skills for self-survival. It is the education that is geared towards the development of the human resource potentials of the society. Kayode and Adagba (2014) view functional education as the education in which the ability to perform productive tasks is more emphasized than the education that aims at producing ideological conformity. For these authors, functional education is not just seen as general education which is an art of acquisition and utilization of knowledge or primarily preparing the youth for examination, but education which goes beyond theory to practice. Kayode and Adagba (2012) also defined functional education as a process activity which involves practical exercises, and outcome of skills, knowledge acquisition which makes the citizen a better and more productive person to him as well as to the society at large. They maintained that for education to be functional, it will yield positive results for both the individual that acquired it and the society at large. This will help the individual to realistically live and appropriately face daily challenges prevalent in one's immediate

environment. Functional education most especially at the secondary school level will aid in equipping man with the appropriate skills that will enhance his productivity in the society. The FRN (2013) in its National Policy on Education sees functional education as the education par-excellence for effecting national economic development. In this regard, functional secondary education will aid Nigeria including Anambra State achieve sustainable national development through the attainment of both educational and national goals. The critical issues here are: Is the Nigeria secondary education system attracting practical result or the possession of certificates instead of on what one can do. The result of this dysfunctional education is that schools' turnout graduates without useful knowledge, competences and skills and who become alienated from the values of their own environment. Hence the need for sustainable national development.

The need of sustainable national development become more crucial as it connotes the ability to keep going and keep up the progress made in various segments of the society. In fact, development is sustainable, *"if it meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs"* (Briggs, 2008). Sustainable national development is a process of improving the range of opportunities that will enable individual humans and communities to achieve their aspirations and full potential over a sustained period of time while maintaining the resilience of economic, social and environmental systems. Sustainable development recognizes three important aspects of development namely: raising people's living level, that is, their income and consumption levels of food, medical services and so on, through relevant economic growth processes, creating conditions conducive to the growth of people's self-esteem through the establishment of social, political and economic system and institutions which promotes human dignity and respect; and increasing people's freedom to choose by enlarging the range of their choice available (Nakpodia and Obielumani, 2012). They further said that for education to be functional for man's benefits, the goods and services should be increased for human consumption and that the environment needs to be preserved in the present in order not to affect future generations' well-being. Sustainability of national development involves supporting and maintaining continuity of the economic development of the nation. It includes providing the necessary items that are required to keep development in position by holding on the standard or goals set by the nation.

Managing education at secondary school level for the sustainable development through leadership practices involves sustaining the teachers and students' interest in the teaching and learning activities in the school. Sustainability depends on the degree to which participants (students and teachers) benefit directly from the educational services. However functional education at secondary school level can be achieved through effective leadership practices for sustainable national development in the Nigeria and Anambra State inclusive.

From the above, school leadership seems to directly dealt with the principal who is the chief executive and also at the helm of affairs that runs the day-to-day activities of the school. The principal is mandated with such responsibility as managing and

improving the educational programme, selecting and developing personnel, working with the community, and managing the school affairs. H is seen as the instructional leader of the organization, supervisor, manager, school climate developer, and a change facilitator as well as performing the following functions such as personnel/staff functions, student functions and educational facilities functions. All these functions will be made functional through effective leadership practices. Leadership practices according to Onuselogu and Uzoechina (2015) is the competencies required for effective and efficient planning, staffing, organizing, coordinating, controlling, decision-making, and initiating of actions for effective management of school. They observed that the behaviours and practices of the principal as chief executive have influence on all aspects of the learning community, which leads to school success. Leadership practices is the ability of the leader to plan, organize, control and direct the operations of an educational enterprise for the purpose of achieving the objectives set for the educational system as a whole. The principal should demonstrate sound leadership practices that will impact positively in the school and such leadership practices include the following: constantly supervising teachers work in the classroom, communicating effectively with the teachers by collaborating, selecting, supporting, and assigning duties to teachers, improving teachers' performances, evaluating students' performance, diagnosing teachers' and students' areas of strength and weaknesses, assisting to find solution(s) to both teachers and students personal and instructional problems, stimulating and providing opportunities for professional (Akpakwu, 2012).

The question which needs to be tackled is what then can the principals do to achieve functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State? The principal should promote functional secondary education and sustainable development in the society through leadership practices which involves the following functions: building teacher-teacher relationship/ collaborations, teacher-student relationship, the teacher-school administrators' harmonious relationship, school-community relationship, among others. The principal should also apply good leadership practices by playing the crucial role by being hard working, friendly, democratic style of leadership/transactional and transformational, accommodative, considerate, and collaborative. He should also play instructional roles such as supervising instructions using various techniques, inspect school diary, collect and issue instructional materials, maintain physical facilities, attend to both students' and teachers' problems, maintain discipline, maintain relationships with parents and community, ensure good condition of work by promoting good school climate (Fullan, 2005).

Principals are the drawing force behind any school and the key to improving the quality of learning process. They engage in the process of curriculum implementation reform everyday of their school leadership life as they initiate curriculum changes and implement decisions on educational inventions improvement (Olibie, 2010). Grimmert cited in Olibie (2010) stated that principals in managing schools effectively should play five key leadership roles and actions in instructional leadership which include: instructional support, collaborative inquiry modeling collegiality and experimentation,

focusing teacher talk on action, helping teachers to frame their inquiry, and connecting action with pupils' learning. The extent to which functional secondary education can be achieved depends greatly on the leadership practices of the principal according to Akpan and Onabe (2016) are as follows - management of students' personnel services. Student personnel services involves all the activities and services that are rendered to students for the achievement of the educational objectives, provision and management of library services, guidance and counseling services, health services and recreational services among others. The principal should as well lead instructions through teaching and learning activities, resource provision and collaborations in the school by engaging in effective leadership practices.

However, effective strategies should be adopted in order to improve leadership practices that will promote functional education in the secondary school level for sustainable national development in Anambra State. In addition, for education to be useful, effective-leadership practices should be given proper attention and made functional for sustainable national development to be actualized. And this remains the thrust of this present study.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Managing functional education at secondary school level through leadership practices for sustainable national development has become one of the major challenges affecting the Nigerian education system in general and Anambra State in particular. The purpose of functional education is to produce individuals with demonstrative skills for self-survival as well as acquisition of knowledge which makes the citizen a better and more productive person to himself and to the society at large. In reality, this seems not realizable because teaching and learning environments in most public secondary schools are poor and uncondusive for effective teaching and learning. However, some researchers has observed some of the challenges militates against actualization of functional education and they include: inadequate funding, insufficient infrastructural and instructional facilities such as functional/ E libraries, laboratories, recreational facilities, well equipped classrooms and workshops, overcrowded classrooms, epileptic internet services, obsolete computers, deplorable states of environment. Again, a lot of principals are yet to apply effective collaborative leadership practices both within and outside the school. If the principal fails to apply practical and experimental learning methods which will enhance the learner to acquire necessary skills and knowledge, then their knowledge becomes obsolete which could be a challenge towards actualization of proper functional education for sustainable national development in secondary schools in Anambra State. This problem which has warranted the researcher to conduct this present study is also one of the management problems affecting functional education, thereby creating a gap in the secondary education sector in Anambra State. Thus, the need to bridge and fill this existing gap in the secondary education sector to ensure functional education, issues relating to leadership practices and sustainability should be addressed. This means that, to actualize functional secondary education, the indices of

effective leadership practices by the school managers for sustainable national development in Anambra State should be given proper attention.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate ways of managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development through effective leadership practices in Anambra State. Specifically, the study aimed at:

- 1) Determining instructional leadership practices for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State.
- 2) Identifying the areas of students' personnel practices for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State.
- 3) Ascertaining teacher collaborative practices for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State.
- 4) Suggested strategies for managing functional secondary education through effective leadership practices for sustainable national development in Anambra State.

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- 1) What are the instructional leadership practices of principals for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State?
- 2) What are the students' personnel leadership practices of principals for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State?
- 3) What are the teacher collaborative leadership practices of principals for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State?
- 4) What are the suggested strategies of managing functional secondary education through effective leadership practices for sustainable national development in Anambra State?

1.4 Research Method

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. This design involved constructing an instrument questionnaire which enable the researcher gather the necessary information from the sample of a large population of the study (Nworgu, 2015). The study population consisted of all the principals and teachers from all public secondary schools in the six education zones of Anambra State and they are six thousand, two hundred and thirty (6,234). In Anambra State, there were a total of 261 principals and 5,973 teachers that existed in the six education zones. (Source: Anambra State Post Primary Education Board - PPEB, 2020). The sample of this study consisted of 908 respondents' comprising two hundred and twenty (220) principals and six hundred and

eighty-eight (688) teachers selected from public secondary schools constituted the sample size of the study. These samples were selected using the stratified random sampling techniques involves a situation where each element in the population is first stratified in terms of their geographical locations, that is 6 education zones and elements drawn from each zone/stratum in such a way that the relative proportions of the strata in the relative sample are the same as in the parent population (Nworgu, 2015).

A 36 item questionnaire tagged "Managing Functional Secondary Education for Sustainable National Development Questionnaire" (MFSESNDQ) was the main instrument and primary source for data collection. Items on the instrument were arranged into four clusters and measured on a 4 point scale, which rated as Strongly Agree - (SA) 4 point, Agree - (A) 3 points, Disagree - (D) 2 points and Strongly Disagree - (SD) 1 point. The questionnaire was divided into two parts of A and B. part A elicited from the respondents, their personal data including their title and school location while part B contains questionnaire items organized into four (4) clusters in order to enable the participants react to each of the items in the instrument (MFSESNDQ) representing the research questions. The research instrument was validated by three experts from the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Anambra State. These experts validated the instrument based on appropriate of language, adequacy of questions in relation to the purpose of the study and research questions and fitness of its face and content validity. Thereafter, several corrections were effected before the final distribution of copies of the questionnaires was made to the respondents.

Reliability of the instrument was determined through a pilot tests, by sampling 6 principals and twenty-four teachers from 6 public secondary schools in Delta State which were not part of the area of study. The scores obtained from the pilot testing were collated and measured using the Cronbach Alpha method and thereafter an internal consistency reliability value of 0.72 was obtained. This result showed that the instrument was reliable and adequate to collect the necessary data for the study. Copies of the questionnaires were administered through a direct contact and hand delivery process with the respondents.

The researcher also sorted the assistance of six research assistants, who were guided on how to reach out their respondents. These research assistants were given briefings concerning the intentions and purpose of the study as well as directing the respondents to fill the questionnaire. The return rate was 100%. Data collected were analyzed using mean scores and standard deviation. The decision rule was based on the premise that any mean score which is rated 2.50 and above was accepted and regarded as agreeing with the statement, while the mean score which rated 2.49 and below was not accepted and regarded as disagreeing with the statement.

2. Results

Table 1: Mean score and Standard Deviation of Principals and Teachers on Instructional Leadership practices for Managing Functional Secondary Education for Sustainable National development in Anambra State (N = 908 (Principals = 220; Teachers = 688))

S/n	Principal instructional leadership Practices for managing Functional Education in the school	Principals	SD	Decision	Teachers	SD	Decision
1	Communicating the objectives of school programmes to the staff.	2.57	1.13	Agree	2.58	1.11	Agree
2	Enhancing teachers to vitalize Practical -based teaching more than theory	2.48	1.01	Disagree	2.22	1.10	Disagree
3	Demonstrating teaching for teacher to observe in the classroom	2.39	1.01	Disagree	2.46	1.13	Disagree
4	Applying various techniques and approaches in supervising teachers work in the classroom	2.37	1.07	Disagree	2.43	1.12	Disagree
5	Constantly monitoring teaching strategies and methodologies applied by teachers in the classroom	2.13	0.98	Disagree	2.49	1.11	Disagree
6	Actively participating in resolving class room instructional problems for teachers	2.62	1.62	Agree	2.59	1.10	Agree
7	Maintaining and managing facilities in the school in form repairing and replacing of laboratories and tools etc.	2.03	1.02	Disagree	2.35	1.11	Disagree
8.	Evaluating Staff and student's performances	2.60	1.09	Agree	2.54	1.10	Agree
9	Assisting teachers to determine Curriculum content and organization.	2.57	1.12	Agree	2.58	1.14	Agree
10	Providing adequate educational facilities such as teaching aids inform of electronic media etc.	2.29	1.09	Disagree	12.46	1.08	Disagree
11	Observing constantly in the classroom for assurance of school goals.	2.13	0.98	Disagree	2.49	1.11	Disagree
12	Providing Various in-service training for teachers to improve in their instructional practices.	2.64	1.04	Disagree	2.33	1.10	Disagree
Overall mean score and standard deviation		2.36	1.08	Disagree	2.46	1.11	Disagree

Analysis of the result in Table 1 revealed that items 1,6,8 and 9 rated above the acceptable mean score of 2.50, showing that both the principals and teachers unanimously agree with the statements on instructional leadership practices of principals for managing

functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State. All other items 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 10, 11 and 12 rated below the acceptable mean score of 2.50, showing disagreement to majority of the statements. By this analysis, the overall section mean of 2.36 and 2.46 showcases principals negative reactions to majority of the statement on instructional leadership practices for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State.

Table 2: Mean scores and Standard Deviation Respondents on Students' Personnel Practices of Principals for Managing Functional Secondary Education for Sustainable National Development in Anambra State (N = 908 (principals = 220; Teachers = 688))

S/n	Principals Student's Personnel Practices for managing Functional education in the school include	Principals	SD	Decision	Teachers	SD	Decision
13	Ensuring students safety in School.	2.87	0.99	Agree	2.56	1.10	Agree
14	Handling student disciplinary problems.	2.89	1.10	Agree	2.57	1.09	Agree
15	Supervising individual students class work	2.44	1.10	Disagree	2.48	1.14	Disagree
16.	Establishing policy and Procedures for dealing with Students.	2.43	1.10	Disagree	2.43	1.12	Disagree
17	Promoting interactive communication between students and their teachers.	1.54	0.83	Disagree	2.47	1.08	Disagree
18	Providing arrangements for Students' feeding.	2.37	1.14	DISAGREE	2.36	1.08	Disagree
19	Treating every student impartially with respect to their individual differences.	2.77	1.04	Agree	2.51	1.12	Agree
20	Promoting effective School based guidance and counseling services to students' career in the future.	2.41	1.12	Disagree	2.33	1.09	Disagree
21.	Ensuring students proper teaching and learning and Promotion from one level to another.	2.72	1.07	Agree	2.55	1.08	Agree
22	Monitoring students' learning goals achievements.	2.65	1.14	Agree	2.56	1.11	Agree
23	Assisting in establishing students Unions.	2.29	1.04	Disagree	2.34	1.10	Disagree
Section mean and standard deviation		2.49	1.12	Disagree	2.47	1.10	Disagree

Analysis of result in Table 2 revealed the point view of principals and teachers concerning students' personnel practices for managing functional education. In Table 2, items 13,14,19,21 and 22 rated above the accepted mean score of 2.50, showing that both the

principals and teachers unanimously agree with the statements on students' personnel practices of principals for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State. Whereas item 15, 16, 17, 18, 20 and 23 rated below the acceptable mean score of 2.50, showing disagreement to the statement. By this analysis, the respondents reacted discontented that principals were less engage and did not participate or involve fully on students' personnel practices for managing functional secondary education for Sustainable national development in Anambra State.

Table 3: Mean scores and Standard Deviation of Respondents on Teacher Collaborative Practices of Principals for Managing Functional Secondary Education for Sustainable National Development in Anambra State (N = 908 (Principals = 220, Teachers = 688))

S/n	Principal teacher Collaborative Practices for managing functional education in the school	Principals	SD	Decision	Teachers	SD	Decision
24	Encouraging Staff competition in academic matters.	2.12	0.99	Disagree	2.25	1.08	Disagree
25	Encouraging staff to participate in decision making as a way to promote positive learning-School Climate and Culture.	2.53	1.14	Agree	2.14	1.03	Disagree
26.	Engaging teachers into team teaching in the school.	2.04	0.97	Disagree	2.23	1.08	Disagree
27.	Allowing experienced teachers to mentor newly employed teachers to improve their pedagogical skill.	2.36	1.05	Disagree	2.19	1.07	Disagree
28.	Giving chance for teachers' autonomy for instructional leadership inter-school collaboration of teachers with other schools in areas of students' teaching and learning.	2.12	0.99	Disagree	2.25	1.08	Disagree
29.	Encouraging inter-school collaboration of teachers with other schools in areas of Students' teaching and learning.	2.24	1.15	Disagree	2.20	1.08	Disagree
30.	Encouraging teachers to relate with parents pertaining their children school work and academic achievement.	2.42	1.10	Disagree	2.15	1.07	Disagree
Section mean and standard deviation		2.27	1.07	Disagree	2.19	1.07	Disagree

Analysis of the result in table 3 revealed that only item 25 (except for the teachers' column) of the principals' column rated above the acceptable mean score of 2.50, showing that the principals agree with the statement on teacher collaborative practices for managing functional secondary education. The rest of items 24, 26, 27, 28, 29 and 30 rated below the accepted mean score of 2.50, indicating that both the principals and teachers

unanimously disagree with the statements on principals' initiation of teacher collaborative practices in the school for managing functional secondary education. This analysis also indicates Principals' less engagement and involvement in teacher collaborative practices for managing functional secondary education for Sustainable national development in Anambra State.

Table 4: Mean scores and standard deviation of respondents on suggested Strategies of Managing Functional Secondary Education through effective Leadership Practices for Sustainable National Development in Anambra State

S/n	Please indicate suggested strategies for managing functional secondary education through effective leadership practices.	Principals	SD	Decision	Teachers	SD	Decision
31.	Constant supervision of teachers' instruction in the school.	3.29	0.87	Agree	2.95	0.98	Agree
32	Devoting more attention to Improve teaching in the school.	3.33	0.74	Agree	2.79	1.06	Agree
33.	Establishing better school Community relationship in school Administration	3.08	0.98	Agree	2.90	1.04	Agree
34.	Instigation of new curriculum redesign and implementation.	2.04	0.99	Disagree	2.20	1.06	Disagree
35	Strengthening collaborations with teachers and Students.	2.91	0.94	Agree	2.81	1.07	Agree
36	Supporting the management board PPEB to deploy auxiliary Staff in areas of entrepreneurship for strengthening Practical training.	3.16	0.90	Agree	2.77	1.08	Agree
Mean and standard deviation		3.06	0.90	Agree	2.74		

Analysis of the result in table 4 revealed that items 31,32,33,35 and 36 rated above the acceptable mean, showing that both the principals and teachers unanimously agree with the statements which suggested strategies of managing functional Secondary education through effective leadership practices for Sustainable national development in Anambra State, Item 34 rated below the mean score of 2.50 indicating that both the principals and teachers showcase negative reactions with the statement indicating their area of disagreement is the instigation of new curriculum redesign and implementation.

3. Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that the principals were less engaged and do not participate actively in instructional leadership practices for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State. The study also discovered that the principals only provided instructional leadership in communicating the objectives of school programmes to the staff, actively participate in

resolving classroom instructional problems for teachers, evaluating staff and students' performances and assisting teachers to determine curriculum content and organization. The principals' were less and engaged in other areas of instructional leadership practices which include: encouraging teachers to utilize practical- based teaching more than theory, demonstrating teaching for leachers to observe in the classroom, constantly monitoring teaching strategies and methodology applied by teachers in the classroom, applying various techniques and approaches in supervising teachers work in the classroom in order to ensure that basic skills and academic subjects are taught, providing adequate educational materials such as teaching aids inform of electronic media, providing various in -service training for teachers to improve in their instructional practices, etc. This finding agrees and concurs with the study of Olibie (2010) who found that principals provided curriculum and instructional leadership to a little extent. This finding also agrees with Aghadiuno (2010) who found that head teachers in Enugu -State did not engage in instructional leadership practices. The fact that principals did not participate and engage actively on instructional practices, the tendency is that it will have adverse negative impact on Schools, whereby principals show less attention on instructional issues. This will indirectly affect teachers to pay less attention to instructional leadership issues (Olibie, 2010). In a situation where these negative attitudes persist, it will be very difficult to achieve efficient and effective management of functional secondary education for Sustainable national development in Anambra State.

The findings of research question two under table engaged and involved on students' personnel practices for managing functional secondary education for Sustainable national development in Anambra State. The result discovered that Principals' Provided their students personnel practices to a Little extent and these include handing students' disciplinary problems, ensuring Proper teaching and promotion of students, and treating every student impartially with respect to their individual differences. Other students' class work, promoting interactive communication between students and their teachers, establishing policy and procedures for dealing with students, assisting in establishing students' unions, and strengthening for promoting students' career in the future were found wanting. Researchers like Akpan and Onabe (2016) also found that principal provision and effective management of students' personnel guidance/Counseling and recreational services had a positive impact on sustainable secondary education in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. Gayford (2009) Cited in Akpan and Onabe (2016) affirms that in most successful secondary schools, Sustainability is an integral element of a well-planned curriculum alongside special events and activities, which are experienced both within and outside the classroom and these promote students' attitude toward learning. Akpan and Onabe (2016) Indicated concerns that the absence or poor management of students' personnel services in secondary schools can have a negative effect on the products of the educational process vis-a-vis functional secondary education.

The findings of research question three under table 3 discovered principals' less engagement and involvement in teacher collaborative practices for managing functional

secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State. The result indicated that the Principals' did not apply teacher collaborative practices in aspects of engaging teachers into team teaching in the school, allowing experienced teachers to mentor newly employed teachers to improve their pedagogical skills, encouraging inter-School collaboration of teachers with others outside the school in areas of Students' teaching and learning, encouraging staff to unanimously initiate and participate in decision making as a way to promote positive learning -School Climate and culture, encouraging staff competition in Academic matters, etc. This finding do not tally with Akpakwu (2012) who indicated areas where principals could demonstrate sound leadership practices in the School as; constantly supervising teachers work in the classroom, communicating effectively and assigning duties to teachers, improving teachers' performances, evaluating students' Performance, assisting to find solution (s) to both teachers and students personal and instructional problems as well as stimulating and providing opportunities for professional, among others. This finding agrees and concurs with the findings of King (2006) study which confirmed that principals worked together with a supportive base of parents, teachers and community members to mobilize initiative. Their efforts broadly focused along two basic dimensions, thus reaching out to parents and community to strengthen the ties between local school professionals and working teachers to promote the formation of a coherent professional community. Spillane cited in Olibie (2010) also noted that team building, teacher empowerment, delegation of authority, use of information technology and increased community participation in provision of resources are parts of the implementation of curriculum reforms process and managing school.

Finally, the findings of research question four under table 4 revealed the suggested strategies of managing functional secondary education through effective leadership practices for sustainable national development in Anambra State, as they include: Improving instructional leadership practices by supporting the management board - PPEB to deploy auxiliary staff in areas of entrepreneurship for strengthening practical training constant supervision of teachers' instructions in the school, devoting more attention to improve practical teaching in the school, establishing better school - community relationships in school administration; strengthening collaborations with teachers and students. The findings agree with Akpakwu (2012) Akpan and Onabe (2016) whose findings agrees that applying effective leadership roles, actions and strategies would lead to schools' and curriculum improvement. Kayode and Adagba (2014), Corroborated that functional education should be assured when issues relating to leadership practices and sustainability should both quantify teaching and learning as well as adoption of sustainable behaviour and whereby these strategies are effectively adopted, they will give room for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State.

4. Conclusion

Effective leadership practice is indispensable for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State. When principals engage and apply strategies that will in turn enhance effective instructional leadership practices, students' personnel practices, and teacher collaborative practices, this will go a long way towards making secondary education in Anambra State in particular and Nigeria in general more functional for sustainability with this, National development takes place. The present study however submits that leadership practices should be highly propagated in the secondary education as a way of managing functional education at the secondary school Level. Upon this benchmark, few recommendations were made.

4.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been proffered below:

- 1) The PPEB and Principals should also encourage teacher collaborations in the teaching and learning, and this practice will enhance and promote functional secondary education for sustainable national development. In addition to this, the Principals should engage in such leadership practices that will foster changes in teachers as well as external forces (Parent, Community, Local industries) to participate in managing functional secondary education
- 2) Principals should improve student' learning by actively engaging in students' personnel practices for managing functional Secondary education for Sustainable national development.
- 3) Principals should enhance and utilize effective instructional leadership practices for managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State.
- 4) Principals should adopt and apply most of the suggested strategies in their various institutions as a means of managing functional secondary education for sustainable national development in Anambra State.

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